

A Review - Herbs in Urinary Tract Infection (UTI)

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ABSTRACT

Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) affects various part of the urinary tract. When it affects the lower part it is known as a bladder infection and when it affects the upper part it is known as kidney infection clinically, presence of more than 1 Lakh organisms per ml of midstream sample of urine (MSU) is an indication of urinary tract infection. A pain and burning feeling when you urinate, Urethral discharge containing pus or mucus, Frequent and urgent need to urinate especially at night, Obstructed urinary flow, Lower back pain, Unexplained fever, Cloudy urine with visible blood are the common symptoms of UTI. Cranberry, blue berry, berberine, bearberry, buchu oil etc are found to be effective in urinary tract infection. The fimbriae of E.coli produce two types of adhesins such as mannose sensitive and mannose resistant adhesins that attach to receptors on uroepithelial cells. Proanthocyanidin obtained from cranberry, blueberry etc shows extreme inhibitory activity against mannose-resistant adhesins. In bearberry the active antimicrobial activity is shown by aglycone hydroquinone which is released in alkaline urine. Buchu leaf is a diuretic and urinary tract antiseptic Urinary tract antiseptic activity is may be due to its essential oil. The essential oil consists mainly of the monoterpene diosphenol.

Keywords: Urinary Tract Infection, Proanthocyanidin, Adhesins

INTRODUCTION

The urinary system includes that urinary bladder, kidneys, ureters (the tube that carries urine from the kidney to the bladder) and urethra. Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) affects various part of the urinary tract. When it affects the lower part it is known as a bladder infection & when it affects the upper part it is known as kidney infection. This occurs due to colonization and multiplication of organisms. Clinically, presence of more than 1 Lakh organisms per ml of midstream sample of urine (MSU) is an indication of urinary tract infection. The most common cause of infection is Escherichia coli, though other bacteria, virus, fungi or parasite. UTI is more common in female due to shorter urethra & lack of defensive bactericidal prostatic gland¹.

Normally the Urinary tract prevents the growth and multiplication of organism by virtue of the following factors:

A high rate of urine flow

Mucosal defense activity.

Regular complete bladder emptying

UTI classified on the basis of spread of infection to various organs of urinary system:

Lower urinary tract infection

Urethritis (inflammation of urethra)

Cystitis (inflammation of bladder)

Upper urinary tract infection

Ureteritis (inflammation of ureter)

Pyelonephritis (inflammation of kidney)

The following are the risk factors that can caused UTI

Sexual intercourse

Diabetes

Poor personal hygiene

Problems emptying the bladder completely

Having a urinary catheter

Kidney stones

Some forms of contraception

Pregnancy

Menopause

Use of spermicidal and tampons

Heavy use of antibiotics

Symptoms

A pain and burning feeling when you urinate, Urethral discharge containing pus or mucus, Frequent and urgent need to urinate especially at night, Obstructed urinary flow, Lower back pain, Unexplained fever, Cloudy urine with visible blood

Herbal Drugs

Cranberry

Cranberry has long been a popular remedy for urinary tract infections. In Britain, cranberry may refer to the native species *Vaccinium oxycoccos*² while in North America, cranberry may refer to *Vaccinium macrocarpon*³. Cranberries contain 80% water and 10% carbohydrates⁴. Among other constituents are flavonoids, anthocyanins, catechin, triterpenoids, organic acids, and trace of ascorbic acid. The major organic acids are citric, malic, and quinic acids, with small amounts of benzoic and glucuronic acids⁵. Anthocyanin pigments obtained from cranberry pulp are used for coloring applications⁶ It is now known that E. coli, the most common cause of UTI, have hair like fimbria that protrude from their surface. The fimbriae

produce two types of adhesins such as mannose sensitive and mannose resistant adhesins that attach to receptors on uroepithelial cells. Two compounds of cranberries; inhibit *E. coli* adhesins. One of which is fructose that inhibits the mannose-sensitive fimbrial adhesins; other is a high-molecular-weight compound that inhibits the mannose-resistant adhesins^{7,8}. Fructose is present mainly in all fruits but unique polymeric compound, which was later named “proanthocyanidin” present in only *Vaccinium* berries (i.e., cranberries and blueberries). Proanthocyanidin shows extreme inhibitory activity against mannose-resistant adhesins produced by urine isolates *E. coli* but shows moderate antiadherent activity against fecal isolates *E. coli*^{9,10}.

Blueberry

Blueberries contain of 14% carbohydrates, 0.7% protein, 0.3% fat and 84% water. They also contain essential mineral manganese, anthocyanins, polyphenols, vitamin C, vitamin K & dietary fiber^{11,12}. The result indicates that blueberry extracts possess similar anti-adhesive effects against uropathogenic bacteria¹³. Fruit extracts such as guava, mango, orange, grapefruit or pineapple, blueberry are compared for inhibiting binding of bacteria i.e. *E. coli* to uroepithelial cells. Studies showed that the constituents in blueberry extracts i.e. high molecular weight proanthocyanidin inhibited bacteria from adhering to the uroepithelial cells using the mannose-resistant adhesions^{14, 15}.

Berberine

Berberine is an alkaloid present in many plants; it is mainly present in the root, rhizome, and stem bark of the plants. Berberine show the inhibitory effect on the growth of several bacterial pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, and *Bacillus subtilis*¹⁶. It has also demonstrated that growth of clinical isolates of *E. coli* in the presence of berberine sulfate completely inhibited fimbria synthesis¹⁷. Thus, it is effective in UTIs by stopping the migration of the pathogen from the gut, a reduction of *E. coli* load in the gut¹⁸.

Arctostaphylos uva ursi (Bearberry)

In bearberry the active antimicrobial activity is shown by aglycone hydroquinone which is released in alkaline urine¹⁹. In clinical studies extracts of *uva ursi* or isolated arbutin was given to human subjects and their urine is examined against *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* etc. Study demonstrated that the crude extract of *uva ursi* was more effective against bacteria than arbutin by itself^{20,21}. Supporting this, a study demonstrated that growth of clinical isolates of *E. coli* in the presence of *uva ursi* extracts increased the microbial cell surface hydrophobicity, thereby decreasing their ability to adhere to host cells²². Additionally; *uva ursi* has diuretic and anti-inflammatory effects that indirectly aid in its use as an antimicrobial to control UTIs^{23,24}.

Buchu Oil, *Barosma betulina* (*Agathosma betulina*)

It is principally use is in the treatment of chronic diseases of genitourinary tract i.e. Chronic inflammation of the mucous membranes of the bladder, irritable conditions of the urethra, abnormally acidic urine with a constant desire to urinate²⁵. Buchu leaf is a **diuretic and urinary tract**

Figure 1

antiseptic. Urinary tract antiseptic activity is may be due to its essential oil²⁶. The essential oil consists mainly of the monoterpene diosphenol. An in vitro study demonstrated some activity for the alcoholic extract of buchu against microflora typical of urinary tract infections. The essential oil (5 mg/plate) showed considerable activity against all the test organisms²⁷.

CONCLUSION

Natural products have played a very important role in health care and prevention of diseases form thousands of years. From centuries; people used herbal medicines for safety, efficacy, cultural acceptability and lesser side effects. Plant and plant products have utilized with varying success to cure and prevent diseases throughout history. Cranberry, blue berry, berberine, bearberry, buchu oil etc are found to be effective in urinary tract infection.

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REFERENCE

1. A text book of pathophysiology, Nirali Prakashan, Dr.S.L.Bodhankar,N.S.Vyawahare, 2006;11.3-11.5.
2. Stace, Clive (2010), New Flora of the British Isles (3rd ed.), Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, p. 512, ISBN 978-0-521-70772-5.
3. Jump up^ "Vaccinium macrocarpon". Natural Resources Conservation Service PLANTS Database. USDA. Retrieved 11 November 2014.
4. Lenter C. Geigy scientific tables. 8th ed. West Caldwell, NJ: CIBA-Geigy; 1991.
5. Borukh IF, Kirbaba VI, Senchuk GV. Antimicrobial properties of cranberry. Vopr Pitan 1972;31:82.
6. Woo A, von Albe JH, Amundson CH, et al Anthocyanin recovery from cranberry pulp wastes by membrane technology. J Food Sci 1980;45:875.
7. Zafriri D, Ofek I, Adar R, Pocino M, Sharon N. Inhibitory activity of cranberry juice on adherence of type I and type P fimbriated *Escherichia coli* to

- eucaryotic cells. Antimicrob Agents Chemother 1989;33:92-8.
8. Ofek I, Goldhar J, Zafriri D, Lis H, Adar R, Sharon N. Anti-Escherichia coli adhesin activity of cranberry and blueberry juices. N Engl J Med 1991;324:1599.
 9. Howell AB, Vorsa N, Marderosian AD, Foo LY. Inhibition of the adherence of P-fimbriated Escherichia coli to uroepithelial-cell surfaces by proanthocyanidin extracts from cranberries. N Engl J Med 1998;339:1085-6.
 10. Foo LY, Lu Y, Howell AB, Vorsa N. The structure of cranberry proanthocyanidins which inhibit adherence of uropathogenic P-fimbriated Escherichia in vitro. Phytochemistry 2000;54:173-81.
 11. "In-depth nutrition information on raw blueberries, per 100 g, USDA Nutrient Database, Standard Reference version SR-21". Nutritiondata.com. Conde Nast. 2014. Retrieved 28 November 2014.
 12. Jump up Kalt W, Ryan DA, Duy JC, Prior RL, Ehlenfeldt MK, Vander Kloet SP (October 2001). "Interspecific variation in anthocyanins, phenolics, and antioxidant capacity among genotypes of highbush and lowbush blueberries (Vaccinium section cyanococcus spp.)". J Agric Food Chem. 49 (10): 4761–7.
 13. Head, K. A. (2008). Natural approaches to prevention and treatment of the lower urinary tract. Alternative Medicine Review, Vol. 13, No. 3, (September 2008), pp. 227-244 ISSN 1089-5159.
 14. Ofek, I., Godhar, J., Zafriri, D., Lis, H., Adar, R. & Sharon, N. (1991). Anti-Escherichia coli adhesion activity of cranberry and blueberry juices. N Engl J Med, Vol. 324, No. 22, (May 1991), pp. 1599 ISSN 0028-4793.
 15. Ofek, I., Goldhar, J. & Sharon, N. (1996). Anti-Escherichia coli adhesin activity of cranberry and blueberry juices. Adv Exp Med Biol, Vol. 408, pp.179-83 ISSN 0065-2598.
 16. Cernáková, M. & Kostálová, D. (2002). Antimicrobial activity of berberine – a constituent of Mahonia aquifolium. Folia Microbiol, Vol. 47, No. 4, (August, 2002), pp. 375-378 ISSN 0015-5632.
 17. Sun, D., Abraham, S. N. & Beachey, E. H. (1988a). Influence of berberine sulfate on synthesis and expression of Pap fimbrial adhesin in uropathogenic Escherichia coli. Antimicrob Agents Chemother, Vol. 32, No. 8, (August 1988), pp.1274-1277 ISSN 1098-6596.
 18. Rabbani, G. H., Butler, T., Knight, J., Sanyal, S. C. & Alam, K. (1987). Randomized controlled trial of berberine sulfate therapy for diarrhea due to enterotoxigenic Escherichia coli and Vibrio cholerae. J Infect Dis, Vol. 155, No. 5, (May 1987), pp.979-984 ISSN 0022- 1899.
 19. Uva ursi. (2004). In: LaGow, B, chief editor. PDR for Herbal Medicines. 3rd ed. Montvale, NJ: Thomson; pp. 847-851 ISBN 1563635127.
 20. Frohne, D. (1970). The urinary disinfectant effect of extract from leaves uva ursi. Planta Med, Vol. 18, No. 1, (January 1970), pp. 1-25 ISSN 0032-0943.
 21. Kedzia, B., Wrociński, T., Mrugasiewicz, K., Gorecki, P. & Grzewińska, H. (1975). Antibacterial action of urine containing products of arbutin metabolism. Med Dosw Mikrobiol, Vol. 27, No. 3, pp.305-314 ISSN 0025-8601.
 22. Türi, M., Türi, E., Kõljalg, S. & Mikelsaar, M. (1997). Influence of aqueous extracts of medicinal plants on surface hydrophobicity of Escherichia coli strains of different origin. APMIS, Vol. 105, No. 12, (December, 1997), pp.956-962 ISSN 1600-0463.
 23. Beaux, D., Fleurentin, J. & Mortier, F. (1999). Effect of extracts of Orthosiphon stamineus Benth, Hieracium pilosella L., Sambucus nigra L. and Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (L.) Spreng. in rats. Phytother Res, Vol. 13, No. 3, (May 1999), pp.222-225 ISSN 0951-418X.
 24. Kubo, M., Ito, M., Nakata, H. & Matsuda, H. (1990). Pharmacological studies on leaf of Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (L.) Spreng. I. Combined effect of 50% methanolic extract from Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (L.) Spreng. (bearberry leaf) and prednisolone on immunoinflammation. Yakugaku Zasshi, Vol. 110, No. 1, (January 1990), pp.59-67 ISSN 1347-5231.
 25. Felter HW, Lloyd JU. King's American Dispensatory. 18th Edn, 3rd revision. First published 1905, reprinted Eclectic Medical Publications, Portland, 1983.
 26. British Herbal Medicine Association. British Herbal Compendium. BHMA, Bournemouth, 1992.
 27. Didry N, Pinkas M. Plantes Med Phytother 1982; 16: 249.